

STUDY OF THE EXCITATION CROSS SECTION OF ISOMERIC STATES IN (N, 2N) REACTIONS ON THE ^{113}In NUCLEUS

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Annotation

The cross sections and isomeric ratios of (n,2n) reactions on the ^{113}In nucleus were studied using the induced activity method. The experimental isomeric ratios are compared with the results of other studies and calculated using a statistical model of the nucleus.

Keywords: activity, isomer, nucleus, nuclear reaction, gamma spectrometer, nuclear half-life, isotope, radioactivity, cross-section, spin, neutron.

Introduction

The study of isomeric ratios provides information on the reaction mechanism, in particular, the moment of inertia of the nucleus, the spin dependence of the level density, and the nature of transitions between highly excited nuclear states [1-3].

In this work, the excitation cross sections of $^{112m,g}\text{In}$ isomeric states in (n,2n) reactions on the ^{113}In nucleus at a neutron energy of $E_n = 14.1$ MeV were studied using the induced-activity method.

Experimental technique

The NG-150 neutron generator of the Institute of Nuclear Physics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan was used as a fast neutron source [4]. This device allows experiments to measure the yields of nuclear reactions irradiated with fast neutrons of energies satisfying the condition $Q \leq 14$ MeV. The irradiation time with a neutron flux with an energy of 14 MeV is 20 min. The neutron flux was monitored using an aluminum plate of natural isotopic composition, which was irradiated together with the targets. Наведенная γ -активность мишеней измерялась на гамма-спектрометре фирмы Canberra, состоящем из германиевого детектора HPGe. Гамма-спектры мишеней начинались измеряться после паузы 2-50 мин и измерялись в течение 3-120 мин.

For a more accurate determination of the isomeric ratios of yields and cross-sections of nuclear reactions, accurate data on the gamma-spectrometer efficiency are of great importance. In this study, radioactive sources from the OSGI set – ^{22}Na ,

^{57}Co , ^{60}Co , ^{88}Y , ^{137}Cs , ^{133}Ba , ^{152}Eu , ^{241}Am , ^{228}Th – were used to determine the efficiency of a semiconductor detector made of ultrapure germanium (a Canberra HPGe detector). Measurements were carried out at different distances from the source to the detector crystal. Figure 1 shows the dependence of the relative efficiency of the gamma-spectrometer on the energies of gamma radiation (HPGe, OSGI ^{152}Eu , 4.5 cm from the detector).

Fig. 1. Relative efficiency of the gamma spectrometer (HPGe, OSGI ^{152}Eu , 4.5 cm from the detector)

The population of the isomeric and ground levels was identified by the γ -lines. The nuclear physical characteristics of the product nuclei of the (γ, n) and $(n, 2n)$ reactions on the ^{45}Sc nucleus were taken from [5-8] and are presented in Table 1, where Q is the reaction energy, I^π is the spin and parity of the level, $T_{1/2}$ is the half-life of the nucleus, I_γ is the intensity of γ -quanta of a given energy per decay, and p is the branching coefficient of the γ -transition.

Table 1

Spectroscopic characteristics of product nuclei of $(n,2n)$ reactions on the

^{113}In nucleus

Nuclear reactio n	Q, MeV	I^π	$T_{1/2}$	E_γ , keV	I_γ , %	p
$^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112m}\text{In}$	9.445	4^+	20.7 m	155,4	11,2	1
$^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112g}\text{In}$	9.445	1^+	14.4 m	606,4 618,2	1,19 5,29	-

In the case of the (n, 2n) reaction, the cross sections for the formation of the isomeric and ground states and their isomeric ratios σ_m/σ_g were determined. To determine the cross sections for the (n,2n) reactions, the following relation was used:

$$\frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_m} = \frac{S_x \lambda_x \varepsilon_m I_m \theta_m N_m F_m}{S_m \lambda_m \varepsilon_x I_x \theta_x N_x F_x}, \quad (1)$$

where $F(t) = [1 - \exp(-\lambda t_o)] \exp(-\lambda t_n) [1 - \exp(-\lambda t_c)]$;

S is the area of the photopeak in the γ -spectrum; $\lambda=0.693/T_{1/2}$ is the decay constant; ε is the spectrometer efficiency; I is the intensity of γ -quanta of a given energy per decay; θ is the abundance of the isotope used; N is the number of nuclei of the isotope under study in the sample; t_o , t_n , t_c are the irradiation time, pause and measurement time, respectively. The index x refers to the nucleus under study, and the index m refers to the monitor.

Based on the monitor reaction data, the cross sections of the reactions under study were calculated. $^{27}\text{Al}(n, \alpha)^{24}\text{Na}$ ($T_{1/2}=15$ h, $E_\gamma=1368$ keV) was used as the monitor reaction, equal to $\sigma_m = 120.3 \pm 1.2$ mb at $E_n=14.19$ MeV [9]. When determining the cross sections, the statistical error of counting in the photopeak of the measured γ -line, the error in determining the cross section of the monitor reaction, and the efficiency of recording γ -radiation were taken into account.

Results and discussion

The obtained experimental results on the isomeric ratios of the yields of reactions (n,2n) on the ^{113}In nucleus are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 and in Table 2. The energy dependence of the reaction cross-sections on the neutron energy, calculated using the TALYS-1.6 program, is also presented here [10]. TALYS is a computer code system for the analysis and prediction of nuclear reactions, the main purpose of which is to simulate nuclear reactions involving neutrons, photons, protons, deuterons, tritons, ^3He and alpha particles in the energy range of 1 keV-200 MeV.

As can be seen from Table 2, the data from all studies are consistent within the measurement errors. The absolute error of the isomeric ratios of the reaction cross sections is determined by the statistical error of counting in the photopeak of the measured γ -line, the efficiency of γ -radiation detection, and the error in the cross section values of the monitors. This table also presents the theoretical calculations of the cross sections carried out using the TALYS-1.6 software package. Figures 2 and 3 show the excitation function of the $^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112m}\text{In}$ reactions in the energy range of 10-26 MeV. The reaction cross sections were calculated using the TALYS-1.6 software package. In the case of the $^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112m}\text{In}$ reaction, the theoretical calculations are in good agreement with the experimental data. This means that the statistical theory of atomic nuclei is in good agreement with the experimental results.

Table 2
Cross sections of the ground and isomeric states of the reaction $^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112m,g}\text{In}$

E_n , MeV	σ , mb		σ_m/σ_g	ref
	m	g		
14,1	1176 ± 70	280 ± 20	$4,2 \pm 0,4$	this work
14,0*	1139	252	4,5	this work
14,5*	1177	256	4,6	this work
14,1	1240 ± 136	297 ± 33	$4,2 \pm 0,6$	[11]
14,3	1107 ± 62	256 ± 19	$4,3 \pm 0,4$	[12]
14,6	1188 ± 69	303 ± 17	$3,9 \pm 0,3$	[13]

Note: *The cross-sections were calculated using the TALYS-1.6 program.

Fig. 1. Excitation function of the reactions $^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112m}\text{In}$. The reaction cross sections were calculated using the TALYS-1.6 software package.

Fig. 2. Excitation function of the reactions $^{113}\text{In}(n,2n)^{112g}\text{In}$. The reaction cross sections were calculated using the TALYS-1.6 software package.

The density of nuclear levels was calculated using the Beta-Bloch formula [1], the spin part of which has the form

$$\rho(J) = (2J + 1) \exp\left[-(J + 1/2)^2 / 2\sigma^2\right] \quad (2)$$

The quantitative agreement between calculations and experiment was improved by fixing the spin constraint parameter σ . Satisfactory agreement was achieved at $\sigma = 3,10 \hbar$.

Conclusion

The experimental results obtained on the isomeric ratios of yields and cross sections for (n,2n) reactions on the ^{113}In nucleus can be used to elucidate the mechanisms of nuclear reactions, develop theoretical models for describing such reactions, and obtain information on the properties of highly excited states of nuclei. These results can also be used to expand the nuclear database on isomeric ratios. Similar experimental data are currently lacking for most nuclei. The results can also be used in applied nuclear physics.

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